

THE IMPACT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY SERVICE INDUSTRY ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

Peng Xinge

Researcher, Samarkand State university

Abstract: With the development of science and technology, the science and technology service industry has gradually become an important part of the modern service industry. It is an important support for promoting scientific and technological innovation and accelerating the transformation of achievements. We found that the technology service industry can promote economic growth by exerting the effect of technological innovation and industrial transformation and upgrading.

Keywords: science and technology service industry, innovation, industrial upgrading, economic growth.

With the continuous deepening and reshaping of the globalization pattern, the world economy is accelerating from the globalization of products and services to the globalization of innovation, and international competition is more prominently manifested in the competition of comprehensive national strength centered on scientific and technological innovation.

The science and technology service industry is a new engine that promotes technological innovation and the transformation and upgrading of the industrial structure of the times, and is crucial to achieving high-quality economic development. Since the financial crisis in 2008, the economic growth of all countries in the world has generally faced downward pressure, but the integration of technology into the service industry and the innovation and entrepreneurship activities it supports have been very active. Many scholars believe that the technology service industry has gradually become the driving force of economic development.

The promoting effect of science and technology service industry on economic growth is not only reflected in the direct promotion of investment and employment to

economic growth, but more importantly, through the roundabout process of production, it serves technological innovation and efficiency changes in other industrial sectors of the national economy, thereby indirectly promote economic growth.

The reason why the technology service industry can become a key industry that affects technological innovation and economic growth is closely related to the new characteristics of technological innovation. Different from traditional innovation, the new features of innovation activities are the complexity of the innovation environment, the synergy of innovation behavior, the socialization of innovation subjects and the platformization of innovation carriers.

As far as the industry level is concerned, the development level of the technology service industry on both sides of the international technology trade is the specific industry carrier of knowledge spillover and technology absorptive capacity. Therefore, the science and technology service industry is conducive to accelerating the accumulation of R&D human capital, enhancing technology spillovers and “learning by doing” in technological innovation activities, and then promoting original innovation, integrated innovation, and introduction, digestion, absorption, and re-innovation. Based on this, this paper proposes the following assumptions:

Accelerating the transformation of economic growth mode and promoting industrial transformation and upgrading has always been an important goal of macroeconomic policies. However, one of the important reasons for the slow industrial transformation and upgrading for a long time is that science and technology have not played a sufficient role in promoting the upgrading of industrial structure, especially as technology and knowledge are important. The supporting role of the carrier's science and technology service industry on the industry and the economy is not obvious. Under the trend of integrating science and technology into the service economy, the technology service industry is an important link for the transformation of traditional industries to advanced manufacturing and modern service industries (Zhong Xiaoping, 2014). The driving force for the transformation and upgrading of the main body of the enterprise, and the promotion of rationalization and upgrading

of the industrial structure will be the necessary conditions for promoting the transformation and upgrading of the industry in the future.

The role of the technology service industry in promoting industrial transformation and upgrading is to introduce technology into agriculture and traditional manufacturing through technology transfer services, realize the integrated development of traditional industries and modern technology, sharing economy, and service economy, and promote the transformation and development of traditional industries; 2 It is to promote advanced manufacturing and service industries to advance to higher-end fields through R&D services, continuously optimize the factor endowment structure of the middle market, and stimulate the vitality of innovation and entrepreneurship in the whole society, thereby continuously promoting the quality and upgrading of emerging industries. Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following assumptions:

According to our research results we offer following future policy formulation:

First, change the traditional industrialization development thinking and develop a new technology service ecosystem. In the face of changes in the competitive scenario of the new generation of technology and industrial revolution, forward-looking layout of new infrastructure represented by 5G, artificial intelligence, industrial Internet, and Internet of Things should also focus on the development of soft infrastructure centered on technological services. important meaning. Innovate and develop technology intermediary service agencies, build a closer production-university-research model, promote the effective connection between the innovation chain and the industrial chain, break through the "no-man's land" of basic research in the field of core technologies, make up for the shortcomings of core technologies, and grasp the core technologies as a whole In our own hands, we will open up the entire chain and process of the industrialization of science and technology.

Second, build a multi-level scientific and technological service system and develop a new innovative organizational model. Build a multi-level technology service industry system, focus on strengthening the four core service formats of research and development services, technology transfer services, business incubation

services and technology financial services, and form an organic soil to support innovation and entrepreneurship. Strengthen the leading role of research and development services in technological innovation, provide support for private capital to enter the research and development field, encourage the whole society to invest in research and development, especially support private capital in the field of basic research.

Third, strengthen the international technology introduction model of science and technology service interaction, and integrate it into the global unified science and technology innovation service system. Change the traditional international technology import model based solely on the introduction of hardware technology and technology contracts, and turn to the interactive technology import model with the intervention of domestic third-party scientific and technological service agencies, and continuously increase the investment in the digestion and absorption of imported technologies. It is not only conducive to improving the efficiency and success rate of international technology introduction, but also conducive to the establishment of a long-term mechanism for international technical cooperation, and to promote the real transformation of international technical knowledge into the accumulation of domestic technical knowledge. Relying on the global technology transfer market system, promote the integration of scientific and technological service institutions into the global unified scientific and technological innovation service system as soon as possible, and build a symbiotic and win-win industrial community with a shared future.

Fourth, to innovate the system and mechanism for the development of science and technology services, we should focus on strengthening the construction of the talent echelon for science and technology services. Focus on strengthening the echelon construction of various types of talents in science and technology, gather high-end R&D talents with innovation and service highlands, cultivate scientific and technological talents with standardized teachers, and standardize scientific and technological market management talents with vocational education, forming a multi-level scientific and technological service talent echelon. Relax the introduction of

R&D and innovative talents, reduce restrictions on the regional flow of scientific and technological talents, strengthen the incentive mechanism for scientific and technological R&D talents, encourage R&D personnel within the system to participate in enterprise R&D work, and promote the orderly flow of scientific and technological R&D talents between regions and inside and outside the system.

References:

1. Asikainen, A. Innovation modes and strategies in knowledge intensive business services [J]. Service Business, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2015.
2. Brenner T. Capasso, M., Duschl, M. Frenken, K. and Treibich T. Causal relations between knowledge –intensive business services and regional employment growth [J]. Regional Studies, Vol. 52, No. 2, 2017.
3. D’Antone, S. and Santos, J. B, When purchasing professional services supports innovation [J]. Industrial Marketing Management, Vol. 58, N. 5, 2016 .
4. Pina K. and Tether B.S. Towards understanding variety in knowledge intensive business services by distinguish- ing their knowledge bases [J]. Industrial Marketing Management, Vol. 58, No. 5, 2016